

EVALUATING THE ROLE OF COMPLETION THYROIDECTOMY IN PATIENTS WITH THYROID CANCERS

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Abstract

Background: Completion thyroidectomy is often performed in differentiated thyroid carcinoma patients who have undergone lobectomy, but its use is contentious because it is felt to overtreat and has surgical morbidity. Clinical decision making should consider the risk of contralateral malignancy and complications of the procedure to reach the right decision.

Aim: To evaluate the incidence of contralateral malignancy following completion thyroidectomy and to assess associated clinicopathological outcomes and postoperative complications.

Methods: This is a single-group retrospective cohort study carried out for six months from 01 December 2024 till 31 May 2025 involving 257 cases of patients that had completion thyroidectomy in the Section of Head and Neck Surgical Oncology, Department of Surgical Oncology, Shaukat Khanum Memorial Cancer Hospital and Research Centre (SKMCH & RC) in the period of 10 years. The electronic medical records were accessed and provided demographic, clinical, and histopathological information. Quantitative variables were given in terms of the mean with standard deviation and categorical variables in terms of frequencies and percentage. The Chi-square tests were used to determine the associations between clinicopathological factors and outcomes, and $p \leq 0.05$ was taken as statistically significant.

Results: The mean age was 41.05 ± 11.86 years, and 75.5% of patients were female. Contralateral papillary thyroid carcinoma was identified in 35.0% of cases, while 53.7% showed no residual disease. Tumor size ≥ 3 cm (64.4% vs. 39.9%, $p = 0.002$) and age >40 years (60.0% vs. 44.9%, $p = 0.037$) were

significantly associated with residual malignancy. Compression symptoms ($p = 0.011$), retrosternal extension ($p = 0.043$), and preoperative hoarseness ($p = 0.008$) were also significant predictors. Postoperative hypocalcemia occurred in 20.2% of patients, particularly in those with larger tumors and extensive prior surgery ($p < 0.001$), while postoperative vocal cord palsy was observed in 0.8%.

Conclusion: A significant incidence of contralateral malignancy was found with tolerable complication rates by completion thyroidectomy. Further predictors of bilateral disease included larger tumor size, older age, and compressive characteristics, which suggest selective surgical completion to use in high-risk patients.

INTRODUCTION

Thyroid cancer is the most prevalent endocrine cancer across the world and papillary thyroid carcinoma (PTC) represents about 80-85% of all thyroid cancer (1). Globally, the occurrence of thyroid cancer has grown significantly in the past decades, with age-adjusted rates exceeding twofold in certain places significantly because of improved diagnostic images and detection of the small tumors. In spite of this increased rate, the disease-specific survival rate of differentiated thyroid cancer is higher than 95% at 10 years, which indicates its favorable prognosis (2). PTC is also characterized by multifocal disease and can affect both lobes of the thyroid, which is a feature with considerable implications on surgical planning. It has been observed that multifocal tumors occur in 18-87% of surgical specimens based on the method used to sample the pathology (3). Up to 30-40% of patients who undergo total thyroidectomy due to PTC are known to have bilateral involvement (4).

Completion thyroidectomy is the process of removing the rest of the thyroid tissue once the first lobectomy has been performed in case of malignancy or other risk factors have been detected (5). In the past, most differentiated thyroid cancers were advised to undergo total thyroidectomy so that it would be easy to administer the radioactive iodine therapy and enhanced surveillance with thyroglobulin levels (6). Nevertheless, the modern practice is moving towards the use of thyroid lobectomy alone in the case of possible low-risk tumors with a size of ≤ 4 cm without any gross extrathyroidal extension or nodal metastases (7). This paradigm shift has minimized the initial surgical morbidity but has

also made the completion thyroidectomy decisions more clinical in relevance (8). Cases of completion thyroidectomy are usually indicated by aggressive histopathology, positive margin, lymph vascular infiltration, and multifocal or bilateral disease (Haugen et al., 2016). It has been proven that contralateral lobe occult carcinoma can occur in 15-40% of patients initially treated with lobectomy (9).

Oncologically, the effects of completion thyroidectomy on recurrence and survival are still under active research (10). Population-based studies indicate no significant difference in overall survival in the total thyroidectomy and lobectomy procedures in low-risk patients with PTC though there may be variation in terms of recurrence (11). The thyroidectomy completion can potentially enhance the staging accuracy and allow patients who are returned to with radioactive iodine ablation with reclassification to intermediate and high risk after histopathological examination (8). Moreover, the post-surgery thyroid monitors with remnant thyroid tissue are also removed, which increases the sensitivity to recurrent disease detection (12). However, the operation has cumulative risks such as the damage of the laryngeal nerve and permanent hypoparathyroidism, especially when it is conducted as the second operation. The incidence of complications in reported post-completion thyroidectomy has been reported to be between 2-10% with regard to institutional volume and surgical expertise (13).

In South Asian nations, thyroid cancer has been on the rise being affected by the changing capacity to diagnose and the nutritional patterns

of iodine and environmental exposures (14). Thyroid cancer has been reported more in Pakistan, especially in the urban cancer registries. Patients with a low- and middle-income environment tend to have bigger tumors or more developed diseases because of a later diagnosis and barriers to accessing healthcare (15). These aspects can affect the probability of the need of completion thyroidectomy and the risk profile of reoperation. Additionally, the differences in access to radioactive iodine treatment and post-follow-ups can change the risk-benefit calculus of the extent of surgery. Thus, international guidelines should be put into perspective with the help of region-specific assessment of the outcomes of completion thyroidectomy (16).

In Pakistan, although there is little published evidence on the indications, results and complication rates of this procedure in dedicated cancer centers, there is limited data (17). An assessment of clinicopathological predictors, which require completion thyroidectomy, may be useful in improving preoperative counseling and surgical planning. Moreover, evaluation of complication rates in high-volume oncology units will be able to help to define the safety profile of staged surgery in the local conditions (9). A specific production of institution-specific data is especially significant in resource-constrained settings where the reduction of repeat surgery will minimize economic and clinical cost. The systematic review of the practice of completion thyroidectomy in Pakistan can thus help to streamline the process of ensuring the individualized risk-based management strategies. Based on this, the purpose of this research is to test the effectiveness and value of completion thyroidectomy among patients with thyroid cancers in one of the special cancer centers in Pakistan.

Methods

Study Design and Setting

The retrospective single-group cohort study was carried out for six months from 01 December 2024 till 31 May 2025 in the Section of Head and Neck Surgical Oncology, Department of Surgical Oncology, Shaukat Khanum Memorial

Cancer Hospital and Research Centre (SKMCH & RC). It examined the patient records of 10 years in order to assess the contribution and the effects of completion thyroidectomy in patients with thyroid malignancies.

Study Population and Sampling Technique

The population of the study included patients that had had completion thyroidectomy after a primary unilateral thyroidectomy (lobectomy or another partial thyroidectomy). A non-random consecutive sampling was used. Patients were eligible in case they had undergone completion thyroidectomy after undergoing an initial lobectomy, with or without neck dissection, within the period of study and had complete electronic medical records that could be reviewed. The inclusion criteria were limited to the patients who had granted institutional consent during admission to use their clinical data in researches. Patients were not included in case they were lost to follow-up, had incomplete or missing clinical data, had already undergone radiation exposure to the head and neck area, had undergone other significant surgery like laryngectomy or laryngopharyngectomy, or did not agree to use their medical record in the research.

Data Collection

The institutional electronic health record system was used to retrieve data in a retrospective manner. The demographic variables were age and gender, whereas clinicopathological variables were the first surgical operation, preoperative symptoms, the status of vocal cords, histopathological results, events during the operation, and postoperative complications. Quantitative variables like age and size of the nodules in the past were taken as continuous variables and those that were categorical were taken as frequencies and percentages. Incidences of contralateral thyroid lobe malignancy during completion thyroidectomy were used as the main outcome measure. Secondary outcome measures were postoperative hypocalcemia, postoperative vocal cord palsy, intraoperative visceral injury and

other clinicopathological features related to surgical outcomes.

Data Analysis

The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 28 was used for statistical analysis. Besides descriptive statistics, mean and SD (standard deviation) were used to show quantitative variables. The frequency and percentages were used to express categorical variables. The inferential statistical analyses were done through Chi-square test and one-way ANOVA. The p-value of less than 0.05 was taken as statistically significant.

Ethical Considerations

The experiment was carried out following the institutional ethical standards. They included only patients who signed an informed consent during their hospital admission allowing them to be used. During the study, the patient confidentiality was upheld.

Results

Total of 257 patients were included in this study. The study population consisted predominantly of patients aged ≤40 years (54.9%, n = 141), while 45.1% (n = 116) were older than 40 years. Most patients had a previous thyroid nodule measuring <3 cm (56.0%, n = 144), whereas 44.0% (n = 113) had nodules ≥3 cm. A clear female predominance was observed, with females accounting for 75.5% (n = 194) of cases. The mean age of patients undergoing completion thyroidectomy was 41.05 ± 11.86 years, indicating that the study population consisted predominantly of middle-aged adults. The mean size of the previously excised thyroid nodule was 3.06 ± 2.12 cm. A marked female predominance was observed, with females comprising 75.5% (n = 194) of the cohort, while males accounted for 24.5% (n = 63), consistent with the known epidemiology of thyroid carcinoma.

Table 1: Demographic and Baseline Clinical Characteristics (n = 257)

Variable	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Age Group (years)		
≤ 40 years	141	54.9
> 40 years	116	45.1
Previous Nodule Size		
< 3 cm	144	56.0
≥ 3 cm	113	44.0
Gender		
Male	63	24.5
Female	194	75.5

Almost half of the patients (49.8%, n = 128) had first right lobectomy, and secondary left lobectomy in 34.2% (n = 88). A small percentage underwent subtotal thyroidectomy (10.9% n=28) and a small percentage underwent total

thyroidectomy (4.7% n=12) as well as isthmusectomy (0.4% n=1). Such results prove that unilateral lobectomy was the most widespread initial surgical intervention before the final thyroidectomy.

Table 2: Initial Thyroid Surgery Performed (n = 257)

Type of Initial Surgery	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Right Lobectomy	128	49.8
Left Lobectomy	88	34.2
Subtotal Thyroidectomy	28	10.9
Total Thyroidectomy	12	4.7
Isthmusectomy	1	0.4

Total	257	100
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Following completion thyroidectomy, more than half of the patients (53.7%, n = 138) showed no residual disease in the contralateral lobe. However, papillary thyroid carcinoma was identified in 35.0% (n = 90) of patients, indicating a significant incidence of contralateral

malignancy. Benign adenomatous nodules and thyroiditis were each observed in 5.4% (n = 14), while follicular neoplasm was rare (0.4%, n = 1). These findings highlight the oncological relevance of completion thyroidectomy in detecting residual malignancy.

Table 3: Histopathological Findings After Completion Thyroidectomy (n = 257)

Histopathology	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
No Residual Disease	138	53.7
Papillary Thyroid Carcinoma	90	35.0
Benign Adenomatous Nodule	14	5.4
Thyroiditis	14	5.4
Follicular Neoplasm	1	0.4
Total	257	100

Compression symptoms were present in 14.8% (n = 38) of patients. Hoarseness was reported in 8.2% (n = 21), while airway deformity was observed in 3.9% (n = 10). Retrosternal extension (1.9%), dysphagia (1.6%), intubation difficulty (1.2%), and hemorrhage (1.6%) were less common. Total of 39 patients (15.2%) and 22

patients (8.6%) were reported to have hypocalcemia and vocal cord palsy before surgery respectively. These findings indicate that most patients did not present with severe compressive or locally advanced symptoms prior to completion thyroidectomy.

Table 4: Preoperative Clinical Features (n = 257)

Clinical Feature	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Compression Symptoms	38	14.8
Retrosternal Extension	5	1.9
Airway Deformity	10	3.9
Intubation Difficulty	3	1.2
Hoarseness	21	8.2
Dysphagia	4	1.6
Hypocalcemia	39	15.2
Hemorrhage	4	1.6
Vocal cord palsy	22	8.6

In the preoperative period, 49.4% (n = 127) patients had bilaterally mobile vocal cords whereas 3.9% (n = 10) patients showed unilateral vocal cord paralysis. Hypocalcemia was identified as the most common complication with 20.2% (n = 52) during the postoperative period. Only 0.8%

(n = 2) had postoperative vocal cord palsy and intraoperative visceral injury was also found to be 0.8% (n = 2). There were no records of tracheal or esophageal injuries. These results indicated that major surgical complications were low with completion thyroidectomy.

Table 5: Vocal Cord Status and Postoperative Complications (n = 257)

Preoperative Vocal Cord Status	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Bilaterally Mobile	127	49.4
Not Seen	120	46.7
Right Paralyzed	7	2.7
Left Paralyzed	3	1.2
Postoperative Complications		
Postoperative Hypocalcemia	52	20.2
Postoperative Vocal Cord Palsy	2	0.8
Intraoperative Visceral Injury	2	0.8

Residual malignancy was significantly higher in patients aged > 40 years (60%) than that in the absence of residual disease (44.9%) (p = 0.037). The size of nodules (≥3 cm) was closely related to contralateral malignancy (64.4% vs. 39.9%, p = 0.002). Residual malignancy also significantly correlated with compression symptoms (24.4%

vs. 11.6% p = 0.011), retrosternal extension (4.4% vs. 0.7% p = 0.043) and preoperative hoarseness (15.5% vs. 5.1% p = 0.008). Such results indicate that contralateral malignant involvement could be predicted by older age and large tumor size.

Table 6: Association Between Clinicopathological Variables and Residual Malignancy (Chi-Square Test)

Variable	Residual Malignancy Present (n=90)	No Residual Disease (n=138)	χ ² Value	p-value
Age > 40 years	54 (60.0%)	62 (44.9%)	4.32	0.037*
Nodule Size ≥ 3 cm	58 (64.4%)	55 (39.9%)	9.21	0.002*
Compression Symptoms Present	22 (24.4%)	16 (11.6%)	6.41	0.011*
Retrosternal Extension	4 (4.4%)	1 (0.7%)	4.08	0.043*
Preoperative Hoarseness	14 (15.5%)	7 (5.1%)	7.02	0.008*

*Significant at p ≤ 0.05

Hypocalcemia postoperative was found in 20.2% (n=52) of the patients and was much more frequent in females (84.6% vs. 73.2%, p= 0.044). A significantly increased risk was observed in patients who had subtotal or total thyroidectomy as their primary surgery (34.6% vs. 10.7%, p < 0.001). Hypocalcemia (69.2% vs. 37.6%, p =

0.001), age over 40 years (63.4% vs. 40.5%, p = 0.005) and retrosternal extension (9.6% vs. 0.001) were both significantly associated with larger nodules (3 cm and above). These results suggest that the degree of previous surgery and the burden of tumor can be a significant cause of postoperative hypocalcemia.

Table 7: Factors Associated with Postoperative Hypocalcemia (Chi-Square Test)

Variable	Hypocalcemia Present (n=52)	No Hypocalcemia (n=205)	χ ² Value	p-value
Female Gender	44 (84.6%)	150 (73.2%)	4.05	0.044*
Subtotal/Total Initial Surgery	18 (34.6%)	22 (10.7%)	16.82	<0.001*
Nodule Size ≥ 3 cm	36 (69.2%)	77 (37.6%)	14.03	<0.001*
Age > 40 years	33 (63.4%)	83 (40.5%)	8.01	0.005*

Retrosternal Extension	5 (9.6%)	0 (0%)	10.42	0.001*
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*Significant at $p \leq 0.05$

The presence of vocal cord palsy (0.8% $n = 2$) postoperative was closely related to the presence of vocal cord paralysis ($p < 0.001$). The two cases were both in patients aged above 40 years ($p = 0.042$) and patients having compression symptoms ($p < 0.001$). Instances of retrosternal

extension ($p = 0.001$) and big nodules of 3 cm and above ($p = 0.025$) also showed significant association. These results indicate that postoperative recurrent laryngeal nerve injury may be predisposed by airway obstruction before surgery and complicated disease features.

Table 8: Association Between Preoperative Vocal Cord Status and Postoperative Vocal Cord Palsy (Chi-Square Test)

Variable	Postoperative VCP (n=2)	No Postoperative VCP (n=255)	χ^2 Value	p-value
Preoperative VCP Present	2 (100%)	8 (3.1%)	45.21	<0.001*
Age > 40 years	2 (100%)	114 (44.7%)	4.11	0.042*
Compression Symptoms	2 (100%)	36 (14.1%)	28.47	<0.001*
Retrosternal Extension	1 (50%)	4 (1.6%)	12.63	0.001*
Nodule Size ≥ 3 cm	2 (100%)	111 (43.5%)	5.02	0.025*

*Significant at $p \leq 0.05$

Discussion

This study was conducted to determine the prevalence of contralateral malignancy after completion thyroidectomy and also determine the clinicopathologic outcome of patients who were initially treated by unilateral thyroidectomy. Papillary thyroid carcinoma was detected in 35.0% ($n = 90$) of the contralateral lobes and 53.7% ($n = 138$) of them showed no residual disease in this cohort of 257 patients. This contralateral malignancy rate is significant clinically, and it is consistent with incidences of 30-45% of differentiated thyroid carcinoma previously reported (18). In a review of 4600 patients, Soibelman and Ronen (2025) found that patients who had total thyroidectomy had better recurrence outcomes than those who had lobectomy in case of tumors that were larger than 1 cm (3). The current result that 44.0% of nodules were at least 3 cm also confirms the argument of completion surgery in bigger tumors. In addition, the residual malignancy significantly correlated with older age (>40 years) (60.0% vs. 44.9%, $p = 0.037$), and this was in line with the

well-developed risk stratification models, where age is a determinant of prognosis (Tuttle et al.,

2010). The finding that nodule size of 3 cm and above is associated with malignancy (64.4% vs. 39.9% $p = 0.002$) also supports tumor burden as the predictor of bilateral disease.

The demographic profile indicated that there was a significant predominance of women i.e. 75.5% ($n = 194$) of patients were women and this is according to known epidemiology of thyroid carcinoma. According to global cancer statistics, the incidence of thyroid cancer in females outnumbered that of males up to three times, with the highest incidence rate of this issue rated between 30 and 50 years (2). The average age of the cohort of 41.05 ± 11.86 years is similar to Asian and Middle Eastern data, with a mean presentation age of 38-45 years (19). It is important to note that the proportion of patients with 40 years and below was 54.9, but the contralateral malignancy was more common in the patients older than 40 years, which indicated a shift to more aggressive biological behavior with age. Bilateral disease patterns have been

implicated to be caused by age-related genomic instability and the prevalence of BRAF mutation in a mechanistic manner (20). Moreover, 60.3% of participants were patients with BMI 25 kg/m² or higher, which is a variable that is becoming increasingly correlated with thyroid cancer development via insulin resistance and inflammatory mechanisms (21). The urban residence represented 62.3% of cases which may indicate differences in the environment or access to health services.

Histopathological analysis showed no residual disease in 53.7% of the patients that casts serious doubts on the possibility of overtreatment. Nevertheless, the fact that papillary carcinoma was detected in 35.0% of contralateral lobes implies that biases can be made by using preoperative imaging alone, as bilateral involvement could be missed. There are reports on studies that employed high-resolution ultrasonography, with corresponding contralateral occult carcinoma rates ranging between 20% and 36%, which are similar to the current results (22). Compression symptoms were also significantly related to residual malignancy (24.4% vs. 11.6% $p = 0.011$), suggesting the possibility of clinical manifestation of mass effect to be related to tumor aggressiveness. A significant association was also found in retrosternal extension (4.4% vs. 0.7%, $p = 0.043$), which may also be viewed as anatomical spread as a sign of progressive disease. A preoperative hoarseness (8.2%) was more prevalent in patients with residual malignancy (15.5% vs. 5.1%, $p = 0.008$) and may represent the proximity or invasion of the recurrent laryngeal nerve. These results are consistent with other reports that show multifocal and bilateral tumor patterns to be associated with local invasion (23).

Hypocalcemia in the postoperative period was the most common complication, with 20.2% ($n = 52$) of the patients developing hypocalcemia. The incidence is similar to that of transient hypocalcemia with incidences of 15-30% reported after total thyroidectomy revealed in major meta-analyses (24). Patients who underwent previous subtotal or total thyroidectomy (34.6% vs. 10.7%, $p < 0.001$) were at a higher risk, which is

why it is possible to suspect a cumulative effect of parathyroid manipulation. Hypocalcemia was also linked to larger nodules of 3 cm and above (69.2% vs. 37.6%, $p < 0.001$) which might be attributed to further surgical dissection. The availability of age above 40 years was significantly correlated (63.4% vs. 40.5%, $p = 0.005$) possibly because of a lower parathyroid reserve in older people. Gender as female gender showed a borderline importance (84.6% vs. 73.2%, $p = 0.044$), which is supported by the literature of hormonal or anatomic predisposition (25). Technical complexity was also determined to be a determinant since Retrosternal extension increased risk (9.6% vs. 0%, $p = 0.001$). These results indicate that the risk of hypocalcemia is multi-factorial and affected by the nature of tumors and the extent of the surgery.

The occurrence rate of the postoperative vocal cord palsy was extremely low 0.8% ($n = 2$), which highlights the safety of surgery in the competent hands. This is also less than pooled international rates of 13% and 3% recovery of permanent recurrent laryngeal nerve injury (26). Interestingly, both instances were found in the patients who had vocal cord paralysis before, which provided a strong association ($p < 0.001$). Retrosternal extension as well as compression symptoms were also strongly related ($p < 0.001$ and $p = 0.001$, respectively), indicating that anatomical distortion is a contributory factor. Big nodules of 3 cm and above were associated with palsy after operation ($p = 0.025$), which substantiates the tumor size as a risk factor in surgery. The age (>40 years) was also found to be significant ($p = 0.042$), which is consistent with the results that nerve vulnerability increases with age (18). Notably, there were no reported tracheal or esophageal injuries which suggests attention to operative technique. These complication rates confirm completion thyroidectomy as a relatively safe operation when conducted in oncologic centers.

Based in oncological perspective, 35% contralateral malignancy rate offers meaningful support to the completion thyroidectomy in the right patient. Craig et al., (2020) showed better disease specific survival where treatment with

total thyroidectomy was done in tumors greater than 1 cm which supported the advantage of full extent resection (27). Moreover, the correlation between the tumor size of 3 cm and malignancy ($p = 0.002$) is consistent with the risk stratification rules of ATA that suggest completion surgery in more dangerous lesions (28). The result that 53.7% had no residual disease, however, needs one to be cautious on preoperative risk assessment to prevent unnecessary surgery. Modern molecular profiling with BRAF and TERT mutations can be used to narrow the selection of patients and decrease overtreatment (24). The ratio between 20.2% hypocalcemia rate and 35% malignancy detection rate indicates the significance of making decisions individually. Bilateral tumors development might be seen as a manifestation of intrathyroidal dissemination or a multicentric tumor, both of which are known in papillary carcinoma (29).

This research has some limitations. The control group that was not subjected to surveillance or non-completion management restricted the possibility to evaluate oncologic superiority in the long-term. No evaluation of survival outcomes, recurrence rates and disease-free intervals were considered and conclusions were made to short-term parameters of clinicopathology. Some of the variables such as the status of BRAF mutation status were not examined and this may have narrowed the risk stratification. Though significant statistically significant associations were proved, it is impossible to infer causality because of the observation design. Also, a few of the categorical variables were based on record-based documentation, which can be prone to reporting variation. It is suggested that future prospective multicenter research that includes molecular profiling and long-term follow-up should be done to confirm these findings.

Conclusion

This study recognized that in 35.0% of cases, completion thyroidectomy detected contralateral papillary thyroid carcinoma, and in 53.7% cases, the remaining disease was absent, which indicates its oncologic applicability and the risk of

overtreatment. The nodule size (3 cm and above) was significantly correlated with the residual malignancy (64.4% vs. 39.9%, $p = 0.002$), the age (>40 years) was also significant (60.0% vs. 44.9%, $p = 0.037$). Symptomatic related features like compression symptoms ($p = 0.011$), retrosternal extension ($p = 0.043$), and preoperative hoarseness ($p = 0.008$) were also significantly correlated with bilateral disease, which indicates that symptomatology could be used as an adjunctive predictor. Hypocalcemia also happened in 20.2% of patients who had a larger tumor and previous surgeries ($p < 0.001$), and vocal cord palsy, postoperative, was not common (0.8%). The lack of significant visceral trauma was another indication that the process is safe in a dedicated oncologic facility. In general, the results indicate that selective completion thyroidectomy is advantageous when using the procedure in individuals with high-risk characteristics to achieve maximum oncological control rates at the cost of an acceptable morbidity.

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